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DEVELOPMENT OF A NEW NODAL CONNECTION OF STRUCTURAL STRUCTURES MADE OF SQUARE PIPES

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New types of structural units of a spatially-rod structure made of bent-welded closed profiles are selected and investigated, taking into account the ease of manufacture and manufacturability of installation.

Keywords: structural design, knot, bent-welded square profile

The relevance of the topic. There is a need to create quickly manufactured easily prefabricated spatial structures for overlapping spans of 12 – 36m. The structures are used for civil purposes: canopies of bus stations and public transport stops, local and commercial enterprises, gas stations, elements of cafes and catering establishments.

The purpose of the work: Designing a new spatial rod structure made of bent-welded closed profiles, taking into account the simplicity of manufacturing and ease of installation.

Tasks of the work:

- Selection of a new type of structural structures based on the definition of the field of rational application;
- For the adopted structural design, the designs of standard units taking into account the ease of manufacture and manufacturability of installation;

Scientific novelty. A new type of structural design using bent-welded square profiles has been developed.

Overview of schemes and types of spatially rod structures.

Structural structures similar in their geometrical structure to metal crystal lattices are a typical example of a spatial system. A force applied to any node of the structure and arbitrarily directed causes force primarily in the

spatially located rods adjacent to the node, i.e. a spatial reaction similar to the resistance of a continuous system (plate or shell). The structural system does not have traditional connections for metal structures and in some cases runs. Their functions are performed by the bearing rods of belt grids and inclined grating. It is easy to see that even a structural plate, the belt grids of which form square cells and are geometrically changeable in themselves, is in general a geometrically unchangeable system without any connections; the role of connections is performed by inclined braces.

The spatial work of structures is more pronounced under the action of uneven loads. At the same time, the overload of most rods, excluding rods, the output of which turns the system into a mechanism, does not disrupt the normal operation of the structure as a whole due to the ability of the system to redistribute efforts.

Structural plates can be formed by crossing flat trusses in two, three or more directions with the division of the plate into square, triangular and hexagonal cells (Figure 1).

a

b

Figure 1. Overlap schemes of vertical cross trusses:

a, b - when the trusses are located in two directions; *c, d* - the same, in three directions

Figure 2 shows the most characteristic nodal junctions of structural plate elements. At the same time, depending on the method of connecting the elements, they are divided into three main groups:

The first group is bolted connections. These include nodal joints that exclude welding both in factory and installation conditions and allow structures to be assembled only on bolts or other assembly parts (Figure 2- *a, b, c, d*):

- connection of corner rods on overlapping bolts. It is used in the lower nodes of the structural structures of the TSNIISK system, working mainly in one direction (Figure 2- *a*);

- Connection of the "Unistrat" type. Developed by Unistrul Corporation in cooperation with the Steel Structures Laboratory of the University of Michigan (USA). The nodal shape is made by stamping with holes and dowels for connecting bent profile rods on bolts (Figure 2- *b*). Such a nodal connection in domestic construction has not found application in repetitive objects. However, due to its great simplicity, it is recommended to master it for use in mass-produced designs;

- The connection of the Sokol system, consisting of six thin-walled pyramidal parts made of sheets using stamping. These parts are connected to each other and to the elements of the composite bent profile using bolts of normal accuracy. To ensure the necessary rigidity, the parts of the node have stamped protrusions around the hole;

- Node connection "Triodetic". Developed by Fentiman (Canada). The nodal element is a

cylinder, along the formers of which there are grooves with grooved walls. The ends of the rods are pressed along the profile of the grooves, inserted into the cylinder and fixed in the slots of the assembly with two covers connected by a bolt (Figure 2- *d*). The assembly of a structural structure using these nodes is significantly simplified, since only one bolt is required to complete. It is recommended that such a nodal connection be mastered by industry for use in mass-produced structures.

Figure 2. Types of nodes of structural structures

a, g - "TSNIISK"; *b* - "Unistrat"; *c* - "Sokol"; *d* - "Triodetic"; *e* - "MERO"; *f* - "TsNIIPSK"; *h* - "TSNIISK"; *i* - "Octaplatte"; *j* - "TSNIISK".

The second group is combined compounds. This group includes connections in which factory welding is used, and assembly of the assembly is carried out on bolts. Characteristic of this group is the dismemberment of the nodal connection into two groups of parts: the parts of the first group are welded at the factory to the ends of the connected rods (bolt tips, sheet shapes, etc.), and the parts of the second group in the form of

washers, bolts, connectors combine the ends of the rods into a node (Figure 2- e, f, g, h):

- Nodal connections of the "MERO" system, developed in 1938 in Germany; the "Weimar" systems, developed in the GDR, "Markhi" and "Kislovodsk", developed in the USSR by the Moscow Architectural Institute and Giprospectlegconstruction.

In all these systems, the main element is a spherical or hemispherical body with threaded holes into which bolts rotating at the ends of the rods are screwed. In the "MERO" and "Weimar" systems, bolts are attached to the rods using conical tips, in the "MARKHI" and "Kislovodsk" systems - flat cylindrical washers welded to the ends of tubular rods, as well as leash bushings and pin clamps (Figure 2- d).

In contrast to the "MERO" type system, nodal connections of tubular rods on hollow balls (NS system), in which connecting bolts are screwed through a hole in the ball from its inner side, have become widespread in Japan.

- Connection on the flanges. Developed by TsNIIPSK for tubular rods and LenZNIIEP for rolling ones in relation to structural structures assembled from pyramids. The bases of the rod pyramids form a compressed belt grid, the nodal connection of which consists of two flanges with welded rods of belts and braces. The mounting flanges are connected using bolts (Figure 2- f)

- Connection of corner profiles on bolts by means of sheet shapes welded in factory

conditions to long-sized belts. The connection is used in the upper nodes of the structures of the "TSNIISK" system, working mainly in one direction (Figure 2- g);

- bolted connection using spatial shapes welded at the factory from separate sheets (Fig. 2- h).

The third group is connections made using assembly welding (Figure 2- i, j):

- Connection of the "Octaplatte" construction. Developed in Germany by Mannesman. Tubular rods are welded to the ball along the perimeter (Figure 2- i);

- Connection of the "TSNIISK" system. The ends of the tubular rods are flattened and collected in a spatial node; the space formed between the ends of the rods is filled with molten metal (Fig. 2- f). [4].

From the whole variety of structural structures, a structural structure of the Kislovodsk type was chosen as an analog sample (Figure 3). The difference between the proposed design and the existing one is that the new structure consists of bent-welded closed profiles (in Kislovodsk - round pipes). The height of the structure is 2.12 m. At this height, all the rods have the same length. The dimensions of the structure in the plan are 24x24m, capital support in the lower nodes, the structure is supported by four columns, the pitch of the columns is 12 m.

Figure 3. General view of the "KISLOVODSK" type structural structure

The minimum length of the belt element is 3 m, respectively, the size of the belt cells is 3 × 3 m. Purlins and profiled flooring are provided along the nodes of the upper belt.

The structures are used for civil purposes: canopies of bus stations and public transport stops, local and commercial enterprises, gas stations, elements of cafes and catering establishments.

The fundamental difference is the development of new connecting nodes. If in the Kislovodsk structure this connection is bolted,

then in the new design it was planned to create a detachable unit with one bolt and without the use of welding joints at the installation stage.

The procedure for designing a new structure is traditional. At the first stage, for the accepted loads (climatic loads are accepted for the Donetsk region), a static design calculation was performed for the first and second groups of limit states. At the second stage, the selection of cross sections

was carried out. As already noted, square profiles of bent-welded elements were adopted. At the third stage, the design of the nodes was carried out with the specification of the dimensions of the connecting elements when calculating the welds.

The general view of the structure when performing static calculations is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. General view of the design scheme of the structure. Plots of longitudinal forces (N),

After performing the static calculation and selection of all cross-sections, the movements of the entire structure were checked (Figure 5) with the adjustment of the cross-sections of the elements

Figure 5. Analysis of the structure's movements along the Y axis.

The procedure for selecting/correcting cross sections for each of the elements is shown in Figure 6. Typical nodes were cut out of the general scheme, efforts were applied to them and the final layout of the sections was carried out.

Figure 6. Adjustment of the cross-sections of the nodes of the structure.
a is the central node, *b* is the extreme node, *c* is the extreme corner node

As already noted, the design of the nodes was fundamental. For ease of installation and operation, the goal was to get away from precision bolted connections that require additional installation work. For further construction, three standard nodes were identified: the support, the support upper, and the standard upper intermediate.

Node No. 101 is a supporting one, located in the lower belt, consists of nine rods, the rods are connected by 1 bolt, transmits loads to the column from the entire structure, the braces and the lower belt are compressed.

Node No. 93 is located in the upper stretched belt, consists of eight rods, the rods are connected by 1 bolt, the braces and the upper belt are stretched except for element 344.

Node No. 111 is located in the upper stretched belt, consists of eight rods, the rods are connected by 1 bolt, the upper belt is stretched, the braces are compressed.

The general scheme of the elements in the design of the node is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. The general scheme of elements in the design of the node.

- 1-square pipe of the lower and/or upper belt;
- 2- connecting bolt;
- 3- connecting plate of the belt;
- 4- square tube of the brace;
- 5- square pipe (lower/upper belt of spatially rod construction);
- 6- metal vertical connecting plate;

Based on the forces acting in the node, all the connecting elements were calculated: the diameter of the bolt, the thickness of the connecting bars, the catheters and the length of the welds.

A feature of the node is the connection with a single bolt. The bolt is pre-installed in the connecting bar, which already has a hole of the desired diameter, and is welded with a special "reverse" nut to prohibit movement along the axis of the bolt, but allow rotation (Figure. 9, a). After assembling the entire assembly, if the stroke of the "reverse" nut is not enough, special wedge-shaped plates are inserted into the existing gap.

From the calculation it was found that the thickness of the connecting plates is 8...12mm, the diameter of the connecting bolt is 36-48mm.

The spatial scheme of the node is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Diagram of a typical node.
a – connecting bolt; *b* - connecting bars of grid elements;
c – assembly assembly; *d* - wedge;

General conclusions. Based on the analysis of the area of rational use of structural structures by the criterion of ease of manufacture and manufacturability of installation, a new type of spatially rod structure node for connecting elements from bent-welded closed profiles is designed.

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